

Coverage of DOAJ journals' citations through OpenCitations

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Abstract

Citations are the pillar of academia. All scientific studies naturally refer to other works. The study aims to reveal the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations. In addition, the study presents the quantitative status of the references between these sources and points out the trend of availability in the years.

We obtained the input data of our study from DOAJ and OpenCitations platforms by downloading the public data dump of DOAJ articles and the OpenCitations' COCI. In order to improve efficiency and avoid the long search time, we downloaded the entire dataset directly instead of using the API. We filtered these two large datasets by using Python Programming Language and several libraries. In the final step we carried out a visualization of the output data.

We analyzed the coverage of articles in terms of open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations. DOAJ journals receive around 36 million citations and do approximately 113 million citations. 10,5 million of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities. Observing the change in the citations over the years, it can be undoubtedly stated that there has been a remarkable increase trend in the last 20 years.

In order to improve the quality of scholarly communication, the data related to citations must be open and accessible by everyone. DOAJ and OpenCitations are important infrastructures that provide citation data openly. By revealing the coverage of Open Access journals in the above-mentioned organizations and presenting the yearly trend of involved citations in DOAJ we may draw attention to the importance of independent OA infrastructure in academic publishing, and may provide important aspects on why scientific studies should be open.

Keywords: open science, citations, OpenCitations, open access, DOAJ, trend of availability

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Introduction

Scientific works build on previous findings and other studies. Basically, science is a cumulative and comprehensive process by its nature. Making use of the knowledge and methods produced so far is a necessary and inevitable phenomenon that contributes to scientific development and accelerates this process. In this context, it is extremely natural and expected that scientific works refer to each other. Citations are fundamental building blocks of this activity. It is crucial for the development and the sustainability of scholarly communication that all data on citations are open and accessible.

Before proceeding with the details of our study we need to explain some basic terminology to have a better understanding. In this context the brief description of open access and open science, which are two distinct terms with a strong connection, must be done. Open Access is an approach where resources are freely available to those who seek them, and these resources are preserved under a license that allows for secondary usage (Watson, 2015). The main purpose of open access is to open the way for new scientific studies and inventions by presenting resources equally to everyone. Watson (2015) describes open science as the implementation of sharing all data and findings in a complete, accessible and open way that allows others to interoperate and build on it(p.1). Open science is inevitably the goal to be reached. Because in the current closed system, serious payments are made to publishers even though they do not produce any value other than "*typesetting and PDF generation*" (Watson, 2015, p.2)

DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) is an Open Access journal database containing more than 17500 peer-reviewed OA journals in different fields, from all over the world and in different languages. DOAJ's aim is to improve the accessibility, validity, use and effectiveness of peer-reviewed open access journals in a global context, regardless of scientific field, country or language. It is managed by Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA), a UK-based public interest company (DOAJ, n.d.). DOAJ follows the Budapest Open Access Initiative's description for involving an OA journal. "*By “open access” to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself*" (BOAI, 2002, para.3). The sole restriction on

reproduction and dissemination should be to provide writers control over the integrity of their work and the ability to be properly credited and cited. DOAJ provides the article metadata openly that can be downloadable from its website.

OpenCitations is an open infrastructure that aims to make scientific data accessible, especially bibliography and citation data. It was initiated as a one-year project under the direction of David Shotton from Oxford University. The aim of the project was to change the current state of academic publishing and scientific communication. An ontology named OpenCitation Corpus has been built in order to produce and share open citation data. OpenCitations provides many citation indexes by exploiting open data coming from other bibliographic databases. The largest citation index is COCI (the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations). *"It is an RDF dataset containing details of all the citations that are specified by the open references to DOI-identified works present in Crossref"* (OpenCitations, 2022). With the latest update which was done on 26 March 2022 *"COCI contains 1,294,283,603 citations and 72,268,850 bibliographic resources"*. The data in COCI can be queried by using the OpenCitations Indexes SPARQL endpoint. It is possible to retrieve data also by using the COCI REST API.

How can we consider a citation as open? *"A bibliographic citation is an open citation when the data needed to define the citation are freely available, downloadable and reusable"* (Peroni & Shotton, 2018, p.4). According to Initiative for Open Citations for considering a citation open it must be structured, separable and open. The citation must be accessible by programming, in a machine-readable format. In addition, the citation must be analyzable without having to access the cited sources, and must also be freely available and suitable for reuse. (I4OC, n.d.).

There are studies on DOAJ and OpenCitations, but there is no specific study covering both fields in terms of citations. Studies on DOAJ focus more on published articles and journals rather than citations. There are also some studies that focus specifically on citation data. However, these studies measure the value of DOAJ journals by comparing citations found in proprietary citation databases such as the Web of Science (WoS) (Saadat & Shabani, 2012).

There are researches that analyze the published journals on a certain field of study such as economy (N M & Pujar, 2021). The main purpose of these studies is to reveal the approach of the relevant field to Open Access publishing by analyzing the annual trend and country

origin. The study limits itself to English-language journals. Citations are not the main subject of the study, the number of publications is taken into account.

There is a recent study on DOAJ that aims to assess the growth of OA journals based on DOAJ public data dump (Pandita & Singh, 2022). Pandita and Singh (2022) claim that with the growth of Open Access journals, some publishers are abusing the authors and the entire scientific environment by not applying any plagiarism policy and publishing articles without peer-review in order to receive Article Processing Charges (APC) from the author (Pandita & Singh, 2022, p.2). However, DOAJ has a high standard in terms of publishing. In addition to its own standards, DOAJ provides its users a feedback channel where they can notify DOAJ if they come across a suspicious journal (Laine & Winker, 2017).

It is significant to scrutinize the citations made and received by the journals published in an open access journal database such as DOAJ, the change in these citations over the years and the scope of these citations, in order to see the changing paradigm in academic publishing clearly.

In our study our base case is directly coming from the following research questions:

- Which is the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations?
- How many citations DOAJ journals receive?
- How many citations DOAJ journals do?
- How many of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities? What is the trend (increasing? decreasing?) in time of the availability of such citations involving journals in DOAJ?

At this point, it would be quite appropriate to briefly mention our research methodology. Based on our research questions we initialized the progress by collecting the input data coming from DOAJ and OpenCitations platforms in CSV and JSON formats. Data is directly downloaded due to citation quantity and long response time.

This data was filtered with the help of Python Programming Language and various libraries. We visualized output data and discussed the results in the upcoming chapters of the study.

From the very beginning to the end of the study, each step has been published in open access resources including its different versions. We prepared a guide to ensure the reproducibility of our work by publishing a protocol in which we transparently convey all the steps of our work.

Materials and methods

In our study, open science is not just our domain of interest but it is also the mentality that we equipped during the whole process. From the very beginning of the study we followed FAIR data principles. We aimed to make our data findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible. In order to manage these goals we used several open access platforms such as Zenodo, Protocols.io and OpenAIRE. For providing solutions to our aforementioned research questions we initialized the process with the data coming from DOAJ and OpenCitations. We downloaded the public data dump of DOAJ articles in .tar.gz format and the public data dump of OpenCitations' COCI in zipped files which contain several CSV files. We did not deal with any issues downloading data from DOAJ however, we faced some issues with COCI. There were two possible approaches to obtain the data from COCI. The first method was using the API service that OpenCitations provides. The DOIs that come from DOAJ are around 5 million. When we consider that each request containing a DOI addressed to the OpenCitations API, takes an average of 1.2 seconds to return a response, which makes it quite long to conclude the collection of the data necessary for the research in term efficiency. In addition to API, OpenCitations also provides a SPARQL endpoint which again would not be suitable for our research because of the efficiency issue. In fact, this system has much longer response times than the API, although it allows for greater flexibility in research. Because of these reasons we decided to download the entire dataset directly. One of the key aspects in determining our methodology has been efficiency. The main problem of downloading the entire dataset was the amount of data that will be preserved on the hard drive. Especially if one tries to read the data by unzipping the content.

From the DOAJ dump, we created a JSON file named doi.json by running create_json_dois.py. Inside this JSON file by concatenating ISSN and EISSN we created a unique key for each journal, having as values: the ISSN (if it is present), EISSN (if it is present), the title of the journal, the list of all the articles' DOIs.

First, we opened the tar file containing the data. For each journal, we extracted only the information about ISSN and EISSN, and first we verified that for each record in the dump there was always at least one of the two. We then added our unique identifier "ISSN + EISSN" to the set of journals. The extraction of data for the articles was the same as the aforementioned process.

We opened the tar file, then for each article we gathered information about the ISSN and EISSN of the issuing journal, and the DOI of the article. If the article did not have any DOIs registered, we added it to a list that we store separately. If the article had a DOI registered, we added it to the final dictionary to be stored in the doi.json file, which contains the list of DOIs as the value of the unique key of the corresponding journal.

We witnessed the cases where ISSN and EISSN were registered incorrectly within the article dump. We handled this case by aligning the data with the previously created journals set. With the aim of simplifying the next steps we created a separate file for storing articles' DOIs from DOAJ as keys and the ISSN+EISSN" identifier of the journal who published it as value.

```
{
  "1779-627X1779-6288": {
    "title": "International Journal for Simulation and Multidisciplinary Design
    Optimization",
    "pissn": "1779-627X",
    "eissn": "1779-6288",
    "dois": [
      "10.1051/ijsmdo:2008025",
      "10.1051/smdo/2019012",
      "10.1051/smdo/2020004",
      "10.1051/smdo/2020001",
      "10.1051/smdo/2016003",
      ...
    ]
  },
  ...
}
```

Figure 1. An example of an element in the doi.json

After DOAJ data we continued with the OpenCitations data dump and we filtered them using the files obtained from the previous step. Firstly we opened the OpenCitations dump, which is a zip file. We unzipped the first level of files and got a set of repositories. In this way, we managed to not overload the local memory. Then we iterated through all the CSV files in the zip directory. Using the Python library Pandas, we transformed the CSV file into a dataframe.

We then created a dictionary with several filtered versions of the same CSV file, with a dictionary comprehension. Also we obtained a pickle file from the previous step of DOAJ data. In three different dataframes, we have selected the rows that include DOAJ DOIs in the cited column, in the citing column and in both. The last one represents the collection of all the citations that we call, for simplicity, 'open' because they are done by and refer to articles contained in DOAJ journals. This was the most simple way that we judged to be accurate to find out if a citation involved open access journals, as DOAJ is the number one dataset to look in this field.

Then we defined a `general_count_dict` and iterated all over these selected dataframes. For each dataframe we applied the following steps:

1. We created another column with the id of the journal defined inside the file pickle.
2. We used the `group_by` function for filtering operation.
3. In the third step, we added all the records to the previously defined `general_count_dict` using another function (`counter_function`).

At each iteration over the files in the zipped repository, after the `open_cit` dataframe, we saved the `open_cit` version of the CSV as a JSON file inside the `data/queried/OC/open_cit` repository, which will be used for the plotting part.

Also, with each iteration, we saved the updated version of `general_count_dict` inside the `data/queried` repository into a JSON file format. The runtime for this step took approximately 2 hours with a 20 Giga RAM and required at least 200GB of storage available.

Then we merged the data from DOAJ and OpenCitations. First of all we added to the `doi.json` file, which was obtained in the very first step of the process, the information that we acquired from the last step stored in the `general_count_dict`. Information in this dictionary is divided in the same way as in the `doi.json` file: by journals.

We grouped and counted the collection of citations, to and from DOAJ journals by year. The result was stored in a JSON file, named `open_cit_in_years.json` and it covers citations for each year that was found. We also encountered some citations with either a NaN (Not a Number) creation date or a wrong creation date (ex. "2109"). We collected them in another JSON file. We visualized our results in bar and scatter charts using the Plotly Python

Graphing Library. We published all the data that we gathered in Zenodo and also in our Github repository.

Results

RQ1: Which is the coverage, in terms of citations, of the open access journals in DOAJ according to the data available in OpenCitations?

The first table displays the data extracted from DOAJ for our research. The following results concern only articles with DOIs, so a total of 5.8 million articles.

Number of journals indexed in DOAJ	17'570
Number of journals having articles with DOIs	12'708
Number of articles processed	7'442'904
Number of articles without DOIs	1'613'244

Table 1. Data extracted from DOAJ

This second table shows the coverage of open access journals in DOAJ, in terms of citations extracted from OpenCitations, so the total number of citations and references of DOAJ journals.

Citations from DOAJ journals	112'833'189
Citations to DOAJ journals	36'048'741
Citations involving DOAJ journals as citing and cited entities	10'590'234

Table 2. The coverage of open access journals in DOAJ, in terms of citations extracted from OpenCitations

RQ2: How many citations DOAJ journals receive?

Among the over 36 million citations received by open access journals indexed by DOAJ, the following table presents the 10 journals receiving most citations.

Title	Number of articles having DOIs	Citations received	Citations received from DOAJ journals
PLoS ONE	265 300	5 860 172	1 482 782
Nature Communications	35 566	1 279 905	267 674
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	49 207	626 313	231 857
PLoS Genetics	9 658	516 416	111 297
PLoS Pathogens	9 554	486 266	131 821
Emerging Infectious Diseases	11 960	446 807	100 010
Molecules	35 459	440 722	132 214
PLoS Biology	6 374	431 820	81 125
Sensors	40 259	431 422	150 061
Frontiers in Microbiology	23 013	379 363	130 222

Table 3. 10 journals receiving most citations by open access journals indexed by DOAJ

RQ3: How many citations DOAJ journals do?

Among the over 112 million citations done by open access journals in DOAJ, the following table presents the 10 journals doing most citations.

Title	Number of articles having DOIs	Citations	Citations to DOAJ journals
PLoS ONE	265 300	9 450 129	650 059
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	49 207	3 524 355	399 889
Scientific Reports	47 840	1 882 967	175 405
Sustainability	46 149	1 776 121	184 593
Nature Communications	35 566	1 730 563	114 636
Molecules	35 459	1 660 000	152 189
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	41 225	1 565 855	198 220
Frontiers in Immunology	22 630	1 499 385	172 458
Frontiers in Microbiology	23 013	1 264 777	159 413
Sensors	40 259	1 169 834	140 058

Table 4. 10 journals doing most citations in DOAJ

RQ4: How many of these citations involve articles published in open access journals as both citing and cited entities? What is the trend (increasing? decreasing?) in time of the availability of such citations involving journals in DOAJ?

As shown in the table for RQ1, there are over 10.5 million citations involving DOAJ journals as both citing and cited entities according to OpenCitations.

The following graph shows the evolution of the availability of such citations by year.

Figure 2. Timeline of open citations of DOAJ journals in the last 20 year

Discussion

The Open Access ecosystem has grown over the past years. The number of OA journals and published articles is increasing. In the results of our research, we can clearly see the increasing trend over the years. When we look at the output data of our study, it is possible to witness an exponential growth in DOAJ citations, especially in the period between 2017-2020. The increase in the number of citations in parallel with the increase in open access journals and articles over the years indicates that the open access publishing model is gaining more significance. During the study, we explained the importance of making the citation data available. The only approach before open access was to keep this data closed and sell it. Considering how dependent scientific production is on the data of citations, we

can say that this creates an obstacle to science itself. OA aims to end this traditional closed approach.

OA has a number of issues facing it. Foremost among these are predatory journal publishers, who seek to gain financial gain by ignoring all ethical values in this field and abuse open access. The term predatory is used to refer to publishers who abuse the Article Processing Charges (APCs) received from authors (Laine & Winker, 2017). In order to get money from the authors, these journals publish without peer-review, without a comprehensive audit of the data presented by the article, even sometimes without a plagiarism check. One of the ways to identify predatory journals is the high difference between the number of citations the journal does and the number of citations it receives. In the data we obtained as a result of the study, we observed that some journals did not receive any citations, but they made a large number of citations. However, when we examined the aforementioned journals individually, we came to the conclusion that this situation is due to the fact that the current data has not been updated yet. In fact, DOAJ frequently inspects its database as a precaution against predatory publishers, and accepts and evaluates readers' feedback on journals they find suspicious. DOAJ has a seal for journals that meet all the requirements to be a fully open access journal. About 1500 journals currently indexed in DOAJ have their seals.

Conclusions

We answered the research questions that constituted our initial case in the study. We have revealed how many citations DOAJ journals receive, how many citations they make, how many of these citations appear in open access journals as both citing and cited entities, and the trend of change in these citations over the years according to the data available in OpenCitations. The study shows an exponential increase in the annual trend of the citations.

There may be various reasons for this, some may consider that the evolving digital environment and developing opportunities are factors. However, this is not the subject of our study. On the other hand, it is possible to make some inferences based on the results of the study. The number of journals and articles published in DOAJ increases, and the number of citations received and made by DOAJ articles increases in direct proportion to this. As a result of the study, PLOS One, one of the leading publishers in the field of open access, is by far the first among the journals citing and receiving citations from DOAJ journals.

Out of 17.000 journals indexed by DOAJ, more than 12.000 of them have articles identified by DOIs and more than 10.000 of these are involved in citations to and from open access journals (in DOAJ). Within DOAJ, more than 1.6 million of articles do not have a DOI.

Although there are articles without DOI registration and incorrect metadata, DOAJ has an important function in open access publishing. These deficiencies can be corrected over time. Currently, the number of journals that fulfill all the requirements of open access and have the DOAJ seal is around 1500. It is possible to predict that this number will increase over time.

In the future, a detailed study can be carried out on the correlation and reasons for the increase over the years. In addition, a study can be carried out on how DOAJ takes precautions against predatory publishers and how these journals can be identified from the citation data.

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